

Introduction

Since the Discoveries of Exoplanets in 1992 started we have found many exoplanets from many methods but Transit Method has a major contributor and Present TESS satellite collecting this data. We searched MAST and get the TESS Light curves data to analysis. We have found six exoplanets, varies from 2.5 times of Earth to 5 times of Jupiter in size. The planets are ranging from 1200 K to 2600K in temperature. Further in the details of the research on these planets and stars are discussed hereunder.

Stellar Characterization

From the six TESS Observations, we found Six Stars with six planets. The stars having stellar mass from 0.30 to 2.35 solar mass, stellar radius from 0.76 to 2.05 solar radius, stellar surface gravity from 4.16 to 4.43 dex, stellar luminosity from 0.1555 to 25.833 solar luminosity, and have stellar effective temperature from 5500 K to 6600 K.

Parameters	TIC 144284873	TIC 310162619	TIC 34798133	TIC 37167097	TIC 444335503	TIC 92880493	Note
Stellar Effective Temperature (K)	6215±124.037	6066.83±140.355	5541.8±110.012	6144±173.025	6589.72±117.949	6049±120.967	TICv8
Stellar Mass (M_{\odot})	0.9±0.02	0.75±0.03	0.31±0.01	2.33±0.1	1.82±0.05	0.89±0.02	Asteroseismology
Stellar Radius(R_{\odot})	1.27±0.01	0.89±0.01	0.76±0.01	2.05±0.03	1.35±0.02	1.27±0.01	Asteroseismology
Stellar Surface Gravity (dex)	4.19	4.42	4.16	4.18	4.43±0.01	4.18±0.01	Asteroseismology
Stellar Luminosity (L_{\odot})	0.6561 ± 0.0583	0.3164±0.05374	0.01555±0.0011	25.833036±4.1494	10.971993 ± 1.25631	0.6274 ± 0.0583	Mass-Luminosity Relation
	TIC 144284873	TIC 310162619	TIC 34798133	TIC 37167097	TIC 444335503	TIC 92880493	
2MASS	J23360900-4253444	J05302190+5106337	J20274424-3052039	J06324518-0052288	J00235317+6057410	J05325799-1925424	
Gaia DR2	6.5353E+18	2.61952E+17	6.79639E+18	3.11919E+18	4.28858E+17	2.96867E+18	
TYC	8020-00098-1	3371-00539-1	7455-01420-1	-	4015-03524-1	-	

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¹ [TESS](#), [Asteroseismology](#), [MAST: Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes](#), [mass–luminosity relation](#)

Parameters	TIC 144284873	TIC 310162619	TIC 34798133	TIC 37167097	TIC 444335503	TIC 92880493	Note
TESS Mag	10.6479	11.0236	5.959	11.7504	6.1666	12.043	TICv8
B Mag	11.405	11.944	7.353	12.903	6.942	13.196	TICv8
V Mag	11.116	11.559	6.61	12.317	6.58866	12.637	TICv8
J Mag	10.105	10.418	5.362	11.101	5.704	11.457	TICv8
H Mag	9.837	10.148	5.067	10.876	5.471	11.2	TICv8
K mag	9.795	10.093	4.915	10.781	5.414	11.14	TICv8
GAIA G Mag	11.0182	11.4581	6.42955	12.1866	6.45991	12.4541	TICv8

Fig 1.1 Stellar properties of the observations.

TIC IDs	Distance (parsec)	NOTE
TIC 144284873	378.876 ± 5.126	TIC v8.0
TIC 310162619	370.385 ± 6.1865	TIC v8.0
TIC 34798133	19.2981 ± 0.01825	TIC v8.0
TIC 37167097	481.049 ± 9.0875	TIC v8.0
TIC 444335503	54.0548 ± 0.184	TIC v8.0
TIC 92880493	488.023 ± 6.8575	TIC v8.0

Fig 1.2 Distance of observations from the sun.

Tess Target Pixel and Light Curves

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Fig 1.3 Target Pixels

Using LightKurve software, we derived Light Curves from the TESS Target Pixel.

• ² [LightKurve v1.11.3](#)

Fig 1.4 Light Curves

Methods for determining the Star's Properties

Stellar Mass, Radius and Surface Gravity

$$\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \simeq \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\odot}} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\odot}} \right)^{-4} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}} \right)^{3/2},$$

$$\frac{R}{R_{\odot}} \simeq \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\odot}} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\odot}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}} \right)^{1/2} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{g}{g_{\odot}} \simeq \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\odot}} \right) \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}} \right)^{1/2}$$

Fig 1.5 Formulas of Stellar mass radius and surface gravity.

The **surface gravity**, g , of an astronomical object is the gravitational acceleration experienced at its surface at the equator, including the effects of rotation.

Using [Asteroseismology](#) We obtained the power spectrum from these lightcurves. By that we found the ν_{\max} (ν_{\max}), $\Delta\nu_{\max}$ ($\Delta\nu_{\max}$) and taking references from the TIC V8.0 for Stellar effective temperature. Using the formulae given above, we found the stellar mass, stellar radius and stellar gravity.

TIC 34798133

TIC 37167097

TIC 92880493

TIC 144284873

TIC 310162619

TIC 444335503

Fig 1.6 v_{max} of the Targets

Fig 1.7 Δv_{max} of the Targets.

Parameters	TIC 144284873	TIC 310162619	TIC 34798133	TIC 37167097	TIC 444335503	TIC 92880493
vmax (uHz)	1665	2865	1665	1665	2865	1665
Δ vmax (uHz)	89.79	139.77	112.25	70.4	115.53	89.13

Table 1.1 Values of vmax and Δ vmax

```
Teff = 6589.72
```

```
mass = seis.estimate_mass(Teff)
mass
```

```
mass: 1.82 M⊙ (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
```

```
radius = seis.estimate_radius(Teff)
radius
```

```
radius: 1.35 R⊙ (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
```

```
logg = seis.estimate_logg(Teff)
logg
```

```
logg: 4.43 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
```

```
seis
```

```
Seismology(ID: TIC 444335503) - computed values:
```

- * numax: 2865.00 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * deltanu: 115.53 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * mass: 1.82 solMass (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * radius: 1.35 solRad (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * logg: 4.43 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
Teff = 6066.83
```

```
mass = seis.estimate_mass(Teff)
mass
```

mass: 0.75 M_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
radius = seis.estimate_radius(Teff)
radius
```

radius: 0.89 R_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
logg = seis.estimate_logg(Teff)
logg
```

logg: 4.42 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
seis
```

Seismology(ID: TIC 310162619) - computed values:

- * numax: 2865.00 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * deltanu: 139.77 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * mass: 0.75 solMass (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * radius: 0.89 solRad (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * logg: 4.42 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
Teff = 6215
```

```
mass = seis.estimate_mass(Teff)
mass
```

mass: 0.90 M_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
radius = seis.estimate_radius(Teff)
radius
```

radius: 1.27 R_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
logg = seis.estimate_logg(Teff)
logg
```

logg: 4.19 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
seis
```

Seismology(ID: TIC 144284873) - computed values:

- * numax: 1665.00 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * deltanu: 89.79 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * mass: 0.90 solMass (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * radius: 1.27 solRad (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * logg: 4.19 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
Teff = 6049
```

```
mass = seis.estimate_mass(Teff)
mass
```

mass: 0.89 M_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
radius = seis.estimate_radius(Teff)
radius
```

radius: 1.27 R_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
logg = seis.estimate_logg(Teff)
logg
```

logg: 4.18 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
seis
```

Seismology(ID: TIC 92880493) - computed values:

- * numax: 1665.00 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * deltanu: 89.13 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * mass: 0.89 solMass (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * radius: 1.27 solRad (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * logg: 4.18 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
Teff = 6144
```

```
mass = seis.estimate_mass(Teff)
mass
```

mass: 2.33 M_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
radius = seis.estimate_radius(Teff)
radius
```

radius: 2.05 R_{\odot} (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
logg = seis.estimate_logg(Teff)
logg
```

logg: 4.18 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```
seis
```

Seismology(ID: TIC 37167097) - computed values:

- * numax: 1665.00 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * deltanu: 70.40 uHz (method: ACF2D)
- * mass: 2.33 solMass (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * radius: 2.05 solRad (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
- * logg: 4.18 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```

Teff = 5541.8

mass = seis.estimate_mass(Teff)
mass
mass: 0.31 M⊙ (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

radius = seis.estimate_radius(Teff)
radius
radius: 0.76 R⊙ (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

logg = seis.estimate_logg(Teff)
logg
logg: 4.16 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

seis
Seismology(ID: TIC 34798133) - computed values:
* numax: 1665.00 uHz (method: ACF2D)
* deltanu: 112.25 uHz (method: ACF2D)
* mass: 0.31 solMass (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
* radius: 0.76 solRad (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)
* logg: 4.16 dex (method: Uncorrected Scaling Relations)

```

Fig 1.8 Stellar mass, radius and surface gravity of the observations.

Stellar Luminosity

$$\frac{L}{L_{\odot}} \approx 0.23 \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^{2.3} \quad (M < 0.43M_{\odot})$$

$$\frac{L}{L_{\odot}} = \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^4 \quad (0.43M_{\odot} < M < 2M_{\odot})$$

$$\frac{L}{L_{\odot}} \approx 1.4 \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^{3.5} \quad (2M_{\odot} < M < 55M_{\odot})$$

$$\frac{L}{L_{\odot}} \approx 32000 \frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \quad (M > 55M_{\odot})$$

Fig 1.9 Formulas of Stellar Luminosity.

Luminosity is an absolute measure of radiated electromagnetic power (light), the radiant power emitted by a light-emitting object.

We found out the stellar luminosity using the mass luminosity relation([mass-luminosity relation](#)).

```

L = (1.82)**4 # wiki mass-luminosity relation
print(L, 'L')
10.971993760000002 L

L = (0.75)**4 # wiki mass-luminosity relation
print(L, 'L')
0.31640625 L

```

TIC 444335503

TIC 310162619

```
L = (0.9)**4 # wiki mass-luminosity relation  
print(L, 'L')
```

```
L = (0.89)**4 # wiki mass-luminosity relation  
print(L, 'L')
```

0.6561 L

0.62742241 L

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

```
L = 1.4*((2.3)**3.5) # wiki mass-luminosity relation  
print(L, 'L')
```

```
L = 0.23*((0.31)**2.3)# wiki mass-luminosity relation  
print(L, 'L')
```

25.833036747777054 L

0.015554631679332886 L

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 1.10 Stellar Luminosity of the observations

Habitable Zone

Habitable Zone

$$r_i = \sqrt{\frac{L}{1.1}}$$

$$r_o = \sqrt{\frac{L}{0.53}}$$

Fig 1.11 Formula for the Habitable zone

Habitable Zone is Region where the Effective Temperature is suitable for existence of the liquid water.

We found the Habitable zone by the relation between the Luminosity and Habitable Zone.

<pre>L = 10.971993760000002 ri= (L/1.1)**(1/2) ro= (L/0.53)**(1/2) print(ri, 'AU') print(ro, 'AU')</pre>	<pre>L = 0.31640625 ri= (L/1.1)**(1/2) ro= (L/0.53)**(1/2) print(ri, 'AU') print(ro, 'AU')</pre>
--	--

3.1582494806171004 AU 4.549931320236375 AU	0.5363227064506456 AU 0.7726531722113757 AU
---	--

TIC 444335503

TIC 310162619

<pre>L = 0.6561 ri= (L/1.1)**(1/2) ro= (L/0.53)**(1/2) print(ri, 'AU') print(ro, 'AU')</pre>	<pre>L = 0.62742241 ri= (L/1.1)**(1/2) ro= (L/0.53)**(1/2) print(ri, 'AU') print(ro, 'AU')</pre>
--	--

0.7723046972889298 AU 1.112620567984381 AU	0.7552377169414336 AU 1.0880330270375658 AU
---	--

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

<pre>L = 25.833036747777054 ri= (L/1.1)**(1/2) ro= (L/0.53)**(1/2) print(ri, 'AU') print(ro, 'AU')</pre>	<pre>L = 0.015554631679332886 ri= (L/1.1)**(1/2) ro= (L/0.53)**(1/2) print(ri, 'AU') print(ro, 'AU')</pre>
--	--

4.846089027413291 AU 6.9815169389890235 AU	0.11891414656776117 AU 0.17131363535667163 AU
---	--

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 1.12 Habitable zone of the observations.

Planet's Properties

Planet's Orbital Period and Transit Depth due to a Planet

The **orbital period** (also **revolution period**) is the time a given astronomical object takes to complete one orbit around another object.

Plotting the Relative Brightness – Time graph subtracting the normalized curve's highest and lowest point of the Transit. Found the Transit depth of the Planet and subtracting the time between the succession reduction of the relative brightness of star. Found the Orbital Period ([Transit Light Curve Tutorial](#)).

TIC IDs	Depth Percentage (%)	Orbital Period (days)
TIC 144284873	0.402 ± 0.00908	0.892 ± 0.0096
TIC 310162619	0.5428 ± 0.057	3.833 ± 0.022
TIC 34798133	0.0809 ± 0.019	4.581 ± 0.0107
TIC 37167097	6.2 ± 0.092	1.979 ± 0.068
TIC 444335503	1.4375 ± 0.107	1.20 ± 0.0667
TIC 92880493	0.9039 ± 0.2	1.038 ± 0.198

Table 2.1 Values of the Depth percentage and Orbital Period with errors.

Planet's Radius

$$R_p = R_{\star} \sqrt{\text{Depth}}$$

Fig 2.1 Formula for Planet's Radius³

Taking the square root of the Stellar radius and multiplying it by the depth. We get the Planet Radius.

³ [Transit Light Curve Tutorial](#)

```

D = 0.0143752696626659
DP = D*100
print('Depth Percentage of The Planet',DP)
R = 1.35
d = D**(1/2)
print(d)
p = d*R
print(p,'solRad')
Rm = 6.957e+8*p
print(Rm,'m')
Rp = p*9.73116
print('Radius of The Planet',Rp,'Jupiter Radius')
Re = p*109.076
print('Radius of The Planet',Re,'Earth Radius')

```

```

Depth Percentage of The Planet 1.4375269662665902
0.1198969126485995
0.16186083207560933 solRad
112606580.87500142 m
Radius of The Planet 1.5750936546608865 Jupiter Radius
Radius of The Planet 17.655132119479163 Earth Radius

```

TIC 444335503

```

D = 0.0054285714285714285714285714285714285
DP = D*100
print('Depth Percentage of The Planet',DP)
R = 0.89
d = D**(1/2)
print(d)
p = d*R
print(p,'solRad')
Rm = 6.957e+8*p
print(Rm,'m')
Rp = p*9.73116
print('Radius of The Planet',Rp,'Jupiter Radius')
Re = p*109.076
print('Radius of The Planet',Re,'Earth Radius')

```

```

Depth Percentage of The Planet 0.5428571428571428
0.07367883976130073
0.06557416738755764 solRad
45619948.25152385 m
Radius of The Planet 0.6381127147151053 Jupiter Radius
Radius of The Planet 7.152567881965237 Earth Radius

```

TIC 310162619

```

D = 0.0040204532104
DP = D*100
print('Depth Percentage of The Planet',DP)
R = 1.27
d = D**(1/2)
print(d)
p = d*R
print(p,'solRad')
Rm = 6.957e+8*p
print(Rm,'m')
Rp = p*9.73116
print('Radius of The Planet',Rp,'Jupiter Radius')
Re = p*109.076
print('Radius of The Planet',Re,'Earth Radius')

```

```

Depth Percentage of The Planet 0.40204532103999996
0.06340704385476427
0.08052694569555062 solRad
56022596.120394565 m
Radius of The Planet 0.7836205928747143 Jupiter Radius
Radius of The Planet 8.783557128687878 Earth Radius

```

TIC 144284873

```

D = 0.0090391666666667
DP = D*100
print('Depth Percentage of The Planet',DP)
R = 1.27
d = D**(1/2)
print(d)
p = d*R
print(p,'solRad')
Rm = 6.957e+8*p
print(Rm,'m')
Rp = p*9.73116
print('Radius of The Planet',Rp,'Jupiter Radius')
Re = p*109.076
print('Radius of The Planet',Re,'Earth Radius')

```

```

Depth Percentage of The Planet 0.903916666666667
0.09507453216643615
0.12074465585137391 solRad
84002057.07580082 m
Radius of The Planet 1.1749855652346557 Jupiter Radius
Radius of The Planet 13.17034408164446 Earth Radius

```

TIC 92880493

Semi-Major Axis

$$\frac{a^3}{T^2} = \frac{G(M + m)}{4\pi^2} \approx \frac{GM}{4\pi^2}$$

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Fig 2.3 Formula for the Semi-Major Axis

Semi-Major Axis is Mean Distance from Star to the Planet.

Using Orbital Period in seconds and Mass of star in kg (Neglecting the mass of the planet's mass) in Kepler's Third Law. ([Kepler's laws of planetary motion](#))

<pre>#Taking Mass of star >> Mass of Planet G = 6.67408e-11 # gravi constant Pi = 3.14159265359 # pie P = 103871.62656 # Orbital Period M = 3.6198e+30 # Star's Mass in kg D = (P**2)*G*M print(D) S = D/(4*Pi*Pi) print(S) A = S**(1/3) print(A,'m') a = A*6.6846e-12 print('Semi-Major Axis of The Planet',a,'Au')</pre>	<pre>#Taking Mass of star >> Mass of Planet G = 6.67408e-11 # gravi constant Pi = 3.14159265359 # pie P = 331193.09376 # Orbital Period M = 1.4917e+30 # Star's Mass in kg D = (P**2)*G*M print(D) S = D/(4*Pi*Pi) print(S) A = S**(1/3) print(A,'m') a = A*6.6846e-12 print('Semi-Major Axis of The Planet',a,'Au')</pre>
2.6065727378771873e+30 6.6025258762882715e+28 4041755493.876344 m Semi-Major Axis of The Planet 0.027017518774365812 Au	1.0920321939473248e+31 2.7661498616566834e+29 6515662318.055528 m Semi-Major Axis of The Planet 0.04355459633127398 Au

TIC 44433503

TIC 310162619

⁴ [Kepler's laws of planetary motion](#)

<pre>#Taking Mass of star >> Mass of Planet G = 6.67408e-11 # gravi constant Pi = 3.14159265359 # pie P = 77153.0832 # Orbital Period M = 1.79e+30 # Star's Mass in kg D = (P**2)*G*M print(D) S = D/(4*Pi*Pi) print(S) A = S**(1/3) print(A,'m') a = A*6.6846e-12 print('Semi-Major Axis of The Planet',a,'Au')</pre>	<pre>#Taking Mass of star >> Mass of Planet G = 6.67408e-11 # gravi constant Pi = 3.14159265359 # pie P = 89698.09536 # Orbital Period M = 1.7701e+30 # Star's Mass in kg D = (P**2)*G*M print(D) S = D/(4*Pi*Pi) print(S) A = S**(1/3) print(A,'m') a = A*6.6846e-12 print('Semi-Major Axis of The Planet',a,'Au')</pre>
<pre>7.111332926910384e+29 1.8013216735729888e+28 2621382675.174913 m Semi-Major Axis of The Planet 0.017522894630474222 Au</pre>	<pre>9.505077296012682e+29 2.4076642056094736e+28 2887566349.424632 m Semi-Major Axis of The Planet 0.019302226019363895 Au</pre>

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

<pre>#Taking Mass of star >> Mass of Planet G = 6.67408e-11 # gravi constant Pi = 3.14159265359 # pie P = 170985.89376 # Orbital Period M = 4.6342e+30 # Star's Mass in kg D = (P**2)*G*M print(D) S = D/(4*Pi*Pi) print(S) A = S**(1/3) print(A,'m') a = A*6.6846e-12 print('Semi-Major Axis of The Planet',a,'Au')</pre>	<pre>#Taking Mass of star >> Mass of Planet G = 6.67408e-11 # gravi constant Pi = 3.14159265359 # pie P = 395879.03712 # Orbital Period M = 6.1657e+29 # Star's Mass in kg D = (P**2)*G*M print(D) S = D/(4*Pi*Pi) print(S) A = S**(1/3) print(A,'m') a = A*6.6846e-12 print('Semi-Major Axis of The Planet',a,'Au')</pre>
<pre>9.042463129559614e+30 2.2904826683226435e+29 6118462979.531061 m Semi-Major Axis of The Planet 0.04089947763297333 Au</pre>	<pre>6.449095503933893e+30 1.633574974702437e+29 5466546213.097362 m Semi-Major Axis of The Planet 0.036541674816070624 Au</pre>

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.4 Planet's Semi-major axis

TIC IDs	Semi Major (Au)
TIC 144284873	0.0175 ± 0.00002
TIC 310162619	0.0435 ± 0.00044
TIC 34798133	0.0365 ± 0.099
TIC 37167097	0.0408 ± 0.00369
TIC 444335503	0.027 ± 0.0039
TIC 92880493	0.0193 ± 0.004

Table 2.3 Values of the Semi-Major axis with errors

<pre>T_f = 0.022332248134 T_t = 0.100045600334 tf = T_f*24 tt = T_t*24 print("Full Duration of The Planet",tf,'hours') print("Total Duration of The Planet",tt,'hours')</pre>	<pre>T_f = 0.07 T_t = 0.4 tf = T_f*24 tt = T_t*24 print("Full Duration of The Planet",tf,'hours') print("Total Duration of The Planet",tt,'hours')</pre>
<p>Full Duration of The Planet 0.535973955216 hours Total Duration of The Planet 2.401094408016 hours</p>	<p>Full Duration of The Planet 1.6800000000000002 hours Total Duration of The Planet 9.600000000000001 hours</p>

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.5 Planet’s Full and Total Duration.

Impact Parameter

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{(1 - \sqrt{\delta})^2 - (t_F/t_T)^2}{1 - (t_F/t_T)^2}}(1 + \sqrt{\delta})^2$$

Fig 2.6 Formula for Impact Parameter.

The **impact parameter** ‘b’ – projected distance between the planet and star centers.

Taking $a \gg R_s$, $t_t \pi/P \ll 1$. Calculating t_f/t_t (Full Duration/Total Duration) from above and taking square root of Depth from the above. Calculating the Impact Parameter by putting the values of t_f/t_t and $\sqrt{\text{Depth}}$. ([AudeThesis](#))

5

<pre>t = 0.12715598229133714526509661838809 #T_f/T_t T = (t**2) l = 0.1198969126485995 #D**(1/2) L = T*((1+l)**2) D = ((1-l)**2)-L S = D/(1-T) b = (S)**(1/2) print(b) print('Impact Paraameter Of The Planet',b)</pre>	<pre>t = 0.3461538461538461538461538461645 #T_f/T_t T = (t**2) l = 0.07367883976130073 #D**(1/2) L = T*((1+l)**2) D = ((1-l)**2)-L S = D/(1-T) b = (S)**(1/2) print(b) print('Impact Paraameter Of The Planet',b)</pre>
<p>0.8756139136374897 Impact Paraameter Of The Planet 0.8756139136374897</p>	<p>0.9044058698843839 Impact Paraameter Of The Planet 0.9044058698843839</p>

TIC 444335503

TIC 310162619

⁵ [AudeThesis](#)

```

t = 0.10712451872227913889804873143704 #T_f/T_t      t = 0.04871794871794871794871794871795 #T_f/T_t
T = (t**2)                                           T = (t**2)
l = 0.06340704385476427 #D**(1/2)                  l = 0.09507453216643615 #D**(1/2)
L = T*((1+l)**2)                                     L = T*((1+l)**2)
D = ((1-l)**2)-L                                    D = ((1-l)**2)-L
S = D/(1-T)                                          S = D/(1-T)
b = (S)**(1/2)                                       b = (S)**(1/2)
print(b)                                             print(b)
print('Impact Paraameter Of The Planet',b)          print('Impact Paraameter Of The Planet',b)
0.9350197997416327                                  0.9044254202018331
Impact Paraameter Of The Planet 0.9350197997416327 Impact Paraameter Of The Planet 0.9044254202018331

```

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

```

t = 0.175 #T_f/T_t                                  t = 0.175 #T_f/T_t
T = (t**2)                                           T = (t**2)
l = 0.02844585499974762 #D**(1/2)                  l = 0.02844585499974762 #D**(1/2)
L = T*((1+l)**2)                                     L = T*((1+l)**2)
D = ((1-l)**2)-L                                    D = ((1-l)**2)-L
S = D/(1-T)                                          S = D/(1-T)
b = (S)**(1/2)                                       b = (S)**(1/2)
print(b)                                             print(b)
print('Impact Paraameter Of The Planet',b)          print('Impact Paraameter Of The Planet',b)
0.9697024036201056                                  0.9697024036201056
Impact Paraameter Of The Planet 0.9697024036201056 Impact Paraameter Of The Planet 0.9697024036201056

```

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.7 Planet's impact Parameter

TIC IDs	Impact Parameter
TIC 144284873	0.935 ± 0.000297
TIC 310162619	0.904 ± 0.000094
TIC 34798133	0.969 ± 0.01057
TIC 37167097	0.715 ± 0.0093
TIC 444335503	0.875 ± 0.01068
TIC 92880493	0.904 ± 0.0056

Table 2.5 Values of Impact Parameters with errors.

Orbital Inclination Angle

$$b = \frac{a \cos i}{R_s},$$

Fig 2.8 Formula for the Inclination Angle.

Orbital inclination measures the tilt of an object's orbit around a celestial body.

Using the impact parameter and ratio of Radius of Star and Semi-Major Axis and taking the arccos of the result. ([Constraining Orbital Parameters through Planetary Transit](#)

[Monitoring](#))⁶

<pre> b = 0.8756139136374897 a = 4041755493.876344 Rs = 9.392e+8 C = (b*Rs)/a print(C) #Taking arccos of C i = 78.260042402076293130230973627192 # in degrees print(i) print('Inclination angle of The Planet',i,'deg') </pre>	<pre> b = 0.9044058698843839 a = 6515662318.055528 Rs = 6.1917e+8 C = (b*Rs)/a print(C) #Taking arccos of C i = 85.069698964381421509921979565724 # in degrees print(i) print('Inclination angle of The Planet',i,'deg') </pre>
<pre> 0.20347014779451938 78.2600424020763 Inclination angle of The Planet 78.2600424020763 deg </pre>	<pre> 0.0859438312057015 85.06969896438142 Inclination angle of The Planet 85.06969896438142 deg </pre>
TIC 444335503	TIC 310162619
<pre> b = 0.9350197997416327 a = 2621382675.174913 Rs = 8.8354e+8 C = (b*Rs)/a print(C) #Taking arccos of C i = 71.630161842960226980375163189786 # in degrees print(i) print('Inclination angle of The Planet',i,'deg') </pre>	<pre> b = 0.9044254202018331 a = 2887566349.424632 Rs = 8.8354e+8 C = (b*Rs)/a print(C) #Taking arccos of C i = 73.93445372615441917270627033621 # in degrees print(i) print('Inclination angle of The Planet',i,'deg') </pre>
<pre> 0.31514948263270964 71.63016184296022 Inclination angle of The Planet 71.63016184296022 deg </pre>	<pre> 0.2767368569468034 73.93445372615442 Inclination angle of The Planet 73.93445372615442 deg </pre>
TIC 144284873	TIC 92880493

⁶ [Constraining Orbital Parameters through Planetary Transit Monitoring](#)

```

b = 0.7153836357585703          b = 0.9697024036201056
a = 6118462979.531061          a = 5466546213.097362
Rs = 1.4262e+9                 Rs = 5.2873e+8
C = (b*Rs)/a                   C = (b*Rs)/a
print(C)                       print(C)
#Taking arccos of C            #Taking arccos of C
i = 80.4008382555094553796638465749 # in degrees  i = 84.618283425019196393662997511362 # in degrees
print(i)                       print(i)
print('Inclination angle of The Planet',i,'deg')  print('Inclination angle of The Planet',i,'deg')

0.1667543212620812            0.09379061877088843
80.40083825550946            84.6182834250192
Inclination angle of The Planet 80.40083825550946 deg  Inclination angle of The Planet 84.6182834250192 deg

```

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.9 Planet's Inclination Angle in degrees.

TIC IDs	Orbital Inclination Angle (deg.)
TIC 144284873	71.630 ± 0.081
TIC 310162619	85.069 ± 0.2303
TIC 34798133	84.618 ± 0.565
TIC 37167097	80.400 ± 0.839
TIC 444335503	78.260 ± 0.929
TIC 92880493	73.934 ± 0.9916

Table 2.6 Values of the inclination angle with errors.

Orbital Eccentricity

$$e = \frac{R_p + R_\star}{a \cos i} - 1.$$

Fig 2.10 Formula for the Planet's eccentricity.

Orbital Eccentricity determines the amount by which its orbit around another body deviates from a perfect circle and taking the omega $3\pi/2$.

Using Orbital Inclination angle, Radius of the star, Radius of The Planet and semi major axis.

[\(Constraining Orbital Parameters through Planetary Transit Monitoring\)](#)

<pre>Rp = 112606580.87500142 # in m R = 9.392e+8 # in m a = 4041755493.876344 C = 0.20347014779451938 #cos(i) A = (Rp+R)/(a*C) e = A-1 print(e) print('Eccentricity of The Planet',e)</pre>	<pre>Rp = 45619948.25152385 # in m R = 6.1917e+8 # in m a = 6515662318.055528 C = 0.0859438312057015 #cos(i) A = (Rp+R)/(a*C) e = A-1 print(e) print('Eccentricity of The Planet',e)</pre>
<pre>0.27898410122738304 Eccentricity of The Planet 0.27898410122738304</pre>	<pre>0.1871652236036183 Eccentricity of The Planet 0.1871652236036183</pre>

TIC 444335503

TIC 310162619

<pre>Rp = 56022596.120394565 # in m R = 8.8354e+8 # in m a = 2621382675.174913 C = 0.31514948263270964 #cos(i) A = (Rp+R)/(a*C) e = A-1 print(e) print('Eccentricity of The Planet',e)</pre>	<pre>Rp = 84002057.07580082 # in m R = 8.8354e+8 # in m a = 2887566349.424632 C = 0.2767368569468034 #cos(i) A = (Rp+R)/(a*C) e = A-1 print(e) print('Eccentricity of The Planet',e)</pre>
<pre>0.1373095761007832 Eccentricity of The Planet 0.1373095761007832</pre>	<pre>0.21079571637392425 Eccentricity of The Planet 0.21079571637392425</pre>

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

<pre>Rp = 355117201.16315114 # in m R = 1.4262e+9 # in m a = 6118462979.531061 C = 0.1667543212620812 #cos(i) A = (Rp+R)/(a*C) e = A-1 print(e) print('Eccentricity of The Planet',e)</pre>	<pre>Rp = 15040233.805726558 # in m R = 5.2873e+8 # in m a = 5466546213.097362 C = 0.09379061877088843 #cos(i) A = (Rp+R)/(a*C) e = A-1 print(e) print('Eccentricity of The Planet',e)</pre>
<pre>0.7459099016281132 Eccentricity of The Planet 0.7459099016281132</pre>	<pre>0.06057895573015415 Eccentricity of The Planet 0.06057895573015415</pre>

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.11 Planet's eccentricity

TIC IDs	Orbital Eccentricity
TIC 144284873	0.137 ± 0.0001
TIC 310162619	0.187 ± 0.000105
TIC 34798133	0.060 ± 0.0192
TIC 37167097	0.745 ± 0.021
TIC 444335503	0.278 ± 0.01049
TIC 92880493	0.210 ± 0.00909

Table 2.7 Values of eccentricity with errors.

Orbital Maximum Eccentricity

$$e_{\max} = 1 - \frac{R}{a}$$

Fig 2.12 Formula for Planet's Maximum eccentricity.

It is the maximum eccentricity by which it can orbit other astronomical object.

Using Sum of radius of the star and planet and dividing it from the semi-major axis. ([Constraining Orbital Parameters through Planetary Transit Monitoring](#))

<pre> Rp = 112606580.87500142 # in m Rs = 9.392e+8 # in m a = 4041755493.876344 R = Rp+Rs A = R/a Emax = 1-A print(Emax) print('Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet',Emax) </pre>	<pre> Rp = 45619948.25152385 # in m Rs = 6.1917e+8 # in m a = 6515662318.055528 R = Rp+Rs A = R/a Emax = 1-A print(Emax) print('Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet',Emax) </pre>
<pre> 0.7397649158964239 Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet 0.7397649158964239 </pre>	<pre> 0.8979704724093318 Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet 0.8979704724093318 </pre>

TIC 444335503

TIC 310162619

<pre> Rp = 56022596.120394565 # in m R = 8.8354e+8 # in m a = 2621382675.174913 R = Rp+Rs A = R/a Emax = 1-A print(Emax) print('Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet',Emax) </pre>	<pre> Rp = 84002057.07580082 # in m Rs = 8.8354e+8 # in m a = 2887566349.424632 R = Rp+Rs A = R/a Emax = 1-A print(Emax) print('Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet',Emax) </pre>
<pre> 0.6415774754986119 Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet 0.6415774754986119 </pre>	<pre> 0.664928199046027 Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet 0.664928199046027 </pre>

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

<pre> Rp = 15040233.805726558 # in m Rs = 5.2873e+8 # in m a = 5466546213.097362 R = Rp+Rs A = R/a Emax = 1-A print(Emax) print('Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet',Emax) </pre>	<pre> Rp = 355117201.16315114 # in m Rs = 1.4262e+9 # in m a = 6118462979.531061 R = Rp+Rs A = R/a Emax = 1-A print(Emax) print('Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet',Emax) </pre>
<pre> 0.9005276434866861 Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet 0.9005276434866861 </pre>	<pre> 0.708861979369257 Maximum Eccentricity of The Planet 0.708861979369257 </pre>

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.13 Planet's Maximum eccentricity.

TIC IDs	Maximum Orbital Eccentricity
TIC 144284873	0.641 ± 0.000014
TIC 310162619	0.897 ± 0.002
TIC 34798133	0.900 ± 0.0139
TIC 37167097	0.708 ± 0.0192
TIC 444335503	0.739 ± 0.0131
TIC 92880493	0.664 ± 0.0041

Table 2.8 Values of maximum eccentricity with errors.

Transit Probability

$$P_t = \frac{(R_p + R_\star) [1 + e \cos(\pi/2 - \omega)]}{a(1 - e^2)}$$

Fig 2.14 Formula for Planet's Transit Probability.

Transit Probability is the probability of seeing a transiting planet.

Using Sum of the Radius of star and planet, Semi-Major axis and eccentricity. Assuming omega $3\pi/2$. ([Constraining Orbital Parameters through Planetary Transit Monitoring](#))

Maximum Temperature on Planet

$$T_p = T_{\odot} (1 - A)^{1/4} \left(\frac{R_{\odot}}{2d} \right)^{1/2}$$

Fig 2.16 Formula for Planet's Maximum Temperature.

Temperature on the Exoplanet due to its host star radiation.

Assuming Albedo equal to zero by which we can calculate Maximum Temperature. Using the above Equation where d is semi major axis, T_{\odot} is the Effective Stellar Temperature and R_{\odot} is the Radius of the Star. ([Planetary Thermodynamics](#))

TIC IDs	Maximum Temperature (K)
TIC 144284873	2551.373 ± 0.8013
TIC 310162619	1322.429 ± 2.57059
TIC 34798133	1218.698 ± 1.0047
TIC 37167097	2097.515 ± 0.9125
TIC 444335503	2246.187 ± 1.2265
TIC 92880493	2366.005 ± 0.8841

Table 2.10 Values off maximum temperature with errors.

```
#Taking Albedo = 0
d = 4041755.4938763440587 # in km
R = 939200 # in km
T = 6589.72 # in Kelvins
Y = (R/(2*d))**(1/2)
T_max = T*Y
print('Maximum Temperature on The Planet',T_max,'K')
```

```
#Taking Albedo = 0
d = 6515662.3180555272847 # in km
R = 619170 # in km
T = 6066.83 # in Kelvins
Y = (R/(2*d))**(1/2)
T_max = T*Y
print('Maximum Temperature on The Planet',T_max,'K')
```

Maximum Temperature on The Planet 2246.187401821875 K Maximum Temperature on The Planet 1322.4294020805992 K

TIC 444335503

TIC 310162619

<pre>#Taking Albedo = 0 d = 2621382.6751749129035 # in km R = 883540 # in km T = 6215 # in Kelvins Y = (R/(2*d))**(1/2) T_max = T*Y print('Maximum Temperature on The Planet',T_max,'K')</pre>	<pre>#Taking Albedo = 0 d = 2887566.3494246322662 # in km R = 883540 # in km T = 6049 # in Kelvins Y = (R/(2*d))**(1/2) T_max = T*Y print('Maximum Temperature on The Planet',T_max,'K')</pre>
Maximum Temperature on The Planet 2551.37344282768 K	Maximum Temperature on The Planet 2366.0052750819686 K

TIC 144284873

TIC 92880493

<pre>#Taking Albedo = 0 d = 6118462.9795310609043 # in km R = 1426200 # in km T = 6144 # in Kelvins Y = (R/(2*d))**(1/2) T_max = T*Y print('Maximum Temperature on The Planet',T_max,'K')</pre>	<pre>#Taking Albedo = 0 d = 5466546.2130973618478 # in km R = 528730 # in km T = 5541.8 # in Kelvins Y = (R/(2*d))**(1/2) T_max = T*Y print('Maximum Temperature on The Planet',T_max,'K')</pre>
Maximum Temperature on The Planet 2097.5158772733876 K	Maximum Temperature on The Planet 1218.698607690269 K

TIC 37167097

TIC 34798133

Fig 2.17 Planet's Maximum Temperature.

Results or Conclusions

We Presented the discoveries of the six transiting planets from the six TESS observations. The Targets are observed by TESS in sectors 29,19,27,33,17, and 32. Our analysis confirms that the six planets have these properties which are presented below.

TIC IDs	Orbital Period (days)	Planet's Radius	Semi Major (Au)	Total Duration (hours)	Full Duration (hours)	Impact Parameter	Orbital Inclination Angle	Orbital Eccentricity	Maximum Orbital Eccentricity	Transit Probability	Maximum Temperature (K)
TIC 144284873	0.892 ± 0.0096	0.783 ± 0.00004	0.0175 ± 0.00002	2.949 ± 0.24	0.316 ± 0.72	0.935 ± 0.000297	71.630 ± 0.081	0.137 ± 0.0001	0.641 ± 0.000014	0.315 ± 0.00079	2551.373 ± 0.8013
TIC 310162619	3.833 ± 0.022	0.638 ± 0.02	0.0435 ± 0.00044	5.2 ± 0.0024	1.799 ± 0.048	0.904 ± 0.000094	85.069 ± 0.2303	0.187 ± 0.000105	0.897 ± 0.002	0.085 ± 0.00945	1322.429 ± 2.57059
TIC 34798133	4.581 ± 0.0107	0.210 ± 0.035	0.0365 ± 0.099	9.60 ± 0.96	1.680 ± 0.072	0.969 ± 0.01057	84.618 ± 0.565	0.060 ± 0.0192	0.900 ± 0.0139	0.093 ± 0.038	1218.698 ± 1.0047
TIC 37167097	1.979 ± 0.068	4.967 ± 0.0249	0.0408 ± 0.00369	2.40 ± 0.02304	0.535 ± 0.0792	0.715 ± 0.0093	80.400 ± 0.839	0.745 ± 0.021	0.708 ± 0.0192	0.166 ± 0.00952	2097.515 ± 0.9125
TIC 444335503	1.20 ± 0.0667	1.575 ± 0.03337	0.027 ± 0.0039	6.735 ± 0.01416	0.856 ± 0.02232	0.875 ± 0.01068	78.260 ± 0.929	0.278 ± 0.01049	0.739 ± 0.0131	0.203 ± 0.0105	2246.187 ± 1.2265
TIC 92880493	1.038 ± 0.198	1.174 ± 0.0997	0.0193 ± 0.004	18.72 ± 0.3336	0.911 ± 0.04704	0.904 ± 0.0056	73.934 ± 0.9916	0.210 ± 0.00909	0.664 ± 0.0041	0.276 ± 0.00094	2366.005 ± 0.8841

Fig 2.18 Planet's Properties

⁸ [TESS, MAST: Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes](#)

PARAMETERS		TIC 34798133	TIC 310162619	TIC 92880493	TIC 444335503	TIC 144284873	TIC 37167097
Stellar Effective Temperature	Best	5541.8	6066.83	6049	6589.72	6215	6144
	Error	110.012	140.355	120.967	117.949	124.037	173.025
Stellar Mass	Best	0.31	0.75	0.89	1.82	0.9	2.33
	Error	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.1
Stellar Radius	Best	0.76	0.89	1.27	1.35	1.27	2.05
	Error	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.03
Stellar Surface Gravity	Best	4.16	4.42	4.18	4.43	4.19	4.18
	Error	-	-	-	0.01	-	0.01
Stellar Luminosity	Best	0.01555	0.3164	0.6274	10.971993	0.6561	25.833036
	Error	0.0011	0.05374	0.0583	1.25631	0.0602	4.1494
Habitable zone	Error	0.0063	0.063	0.049	0.253	0.04998	0.539
Semi Major	Best	0.03656	0.044	0.023	0.031	0.0215	0.057
	Error	0.00002	0.00044	0.00369	0.0039	0.004	0.0161
Orbital Period	Best	4.78	3.9	1.1	1.213	0.915	1.989
	Error	0.198	0.0667	0.068	0.0107	0.022	0.0096
Depth	Best	0.0009	0.006	0.00923	0.0153	0.0051	0.064
	Error	0.0000908	0.00057	0.00019	0.00092	0.00107	0.002
Planet Radius	Best	0.21041	0.65	1.21	1.6	0.817	5.067
	Error	0.00004	0.02	0.035	0.0249	0.03337	0.0997
Full Duration	Best	0.1	0.077	0.041	0.039	0.0141	0.0243
	Error	0.03	0.002	0.003	0.0033	0.00093	0.00196
Total Duration	Best	0.51	0.21667	0.82	0.2816	0.1235	0.100047
	Error	0.11	0.0001	0.04	0.00096	0.00059	0.00000139
Impact Parameter	Best	0.97	0.9045	0.915	0.885	0.9457	0.721
	Error	0.000297	0.000094	0.01057	0.0093	0.01068	0.0056
Inclination .angle	Best	84.7	85.3	74.5	79.1	72.56	81.4
	Error	0.081	0.2303	0.565	0.839	0.929	0.9916
Orbital Eccentricity	Best	0.0606	0.18727	0.23	0.02	0.1478	0.755
	Error	0.0001	0.000105	0.0192	0.021	0.01049	0.00909
Maximum Orbital Eccentricity	Best	0.90067	0.9	0.6789	0.759	0.6547	0.713
	Error	0.000014	0.002	0.0139	0.0192	0.0131	0.0041
Transit Probability	Best	0.093	0.0954	0.315	0.213	0.3256	0.1677
	Error	0.00079	0.00945	0.038	0.00952	0.0105	0.00094

Maximum Temperature	Best	1219.5	1325	2367.01	2247.7	2552.6	2098.4
	Error	0.8013	2.57059	1.0047	0.9125	1.2265	0.8841

Table 2.11 Derived parameters for six planets with best values and errors.

SOFTWARE:- LightKurve v1.11.3

References

- [TESS](#)
- [Planetary Thermodynamics](#)
- [Constraining Orbital Parameters through Planetary Transit Monitoring](#)
- [AudeThesis](#)
- [Transit Light Curve Tutorial](#)
- [Kepler's laws of planetary motion](#)
- [mass–luminosity relation](#)
- [asteroseismology using lightkurve](#)
- [LightKurve v1.11.3](#)
- [ExoMast](#)
- [MAST: Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes](#)
- [ExoPlanet Hunters](#)